

Stability Control on Ro-Ro Passenger Ships as the Main Factor of Ship's Safety

Dr. Marek Szymoński

Master Mariner, Professor, Naval Academy of Gdynia, Poland

Suggested Citation

Szymoński, M. (2023). Stability Control on Ro-Ro Passenger Ships as the Main Factor of Ship's Safety. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(5), 1033-1041. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(5\).90](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(5).90)

Abstract:

On Ro-Ro passenger ship the wide spectrum of captain's responsibilities should be taken into consideration. One of the important responsibilities is the ship's stability examination. The other measures as the ship's condition, wind on ship with large windage area, rolling characteristics, severe seas etc., are important for ensuring the safe operating of ship, to minimize the risk to the ship, to the personnel and passengers on board, and to the environment. The international convention for the Safety of Life At

Sea – (SOLAS 90) make into fact the continual development of safety standards in the 111 years since the sinking of the Titanic. Important enhancement stability, operational requirements and damage stability requirements were made as a consequence of several disasters at sea: “Torrey Canyon” in 1967, “Herald of Free Enterprise” in 1987 (183 dead), “Exon Valdez” in 1989, “Braer” in 1993, “Estonia” in 1994 (892 dead). In particular the dramatic loss of the Ro-Ro/Passenger vessels M/F “Herald of Free Enterprise” in 1987, and M/F “Estonia” in 1994, respectively, has resulted in the international regulation requiring enhanced damage stability requirements for this type of vessels, and in more stringent damage stability criteria adopted on a regional basis by Northern European countries (Stockholm Agreement, 1977).

Keywords: *safety at sea, ship's stability, damage stability, Ro-Ro vessels.*

Introduction

Ro-Ro / Passenger vessels have a supplementary damage stability regulation. These new regulations based on a wide range of related design parameters, such as the number, positioning and local optimization of transverse bulkheads, the presence and position of longitudinal bulkheads below the main vehicle deck, the presence of side casings, and the height of the main deck and double bottom. The effects of water on deck and of operational parameters as draught, Centre of gravity and trim. The current damage stability standard is that a Ro-Ro vessel should be able to sustain damage to any two adjacent compartments.

Damage Stability Criteria

In northern European countries, an increased standard of damage stability calculations is applied to existing Ro-Ro vessels, known as the Stockholm Agreement, which requires either fulfilment of the deterministic standards of SOLAS' 90 with an additional height of water on deck (maximum of 50 cm), or the demonstration, by means of model experiments, that the Ro-Ro vessel can survive the sea state in a damaged condition.

The damage stability criteria and provisions laid down in the SOLAS 2009 Ch. II-1 Pt. B and Stockholm Agreement are as follows:

1. Range of positive part of the GZ curve >10 DEG;
2. The area under the righting lever curve ≥ 0.015 MRAD;
3. Maximum heeling angle < 12 DEG;
4. Metacentric height > 0.05 m;
5. Maximum GZ $\geq 0,1$ m;
6. Maximum GZ \geq (heeling moment) / (dis-placement) + 0.04 m, taking into account the greatest of the following moments:
 - The wind pressure of 120 N/m²,
 - The crowding of all passengers to-wards one side of the vessel,
 - The launching of a fully loaded davit-launched survival crafts on one side.

The presented paper describes the results of practical use of the stability calculations and damage stability calculations for the Ro-Ro/Passenger vessel M/F “Polonia”, serving in Southern Baltic.

The said vessel is shown in Figure 1.

**Figure 1. M/F “Polonia”
(by UNITY LINE)**

Vessel Characteristics

General

Twin – screw, roll-on, roll-off, rail-truck-cars-passenger vessel, designated for Świnoujście – Ystad route, is arranged as follows:

- Soft nosed and raked stem with bulbous bow,

- Transom stern,
- Two full length cargo decks of 2 670 m total loading lane length, including lifted car shelves, with 6 railway tracks of effective loading length 740 m on the main deck,
- Machinery located aft, with 27.5 m of the engine room length,
- Twin controllable pitch propeller propulsion-plant,
- 4 x STORK-WARTSILA medium speed main engines of 15 840 KW total,
- 3 bow thrusters of 1 600 KW each,
- 1 stern thruster of 1 600KW,
- Heeling compensation INTERING system,
- Three accommodated decks above cargo hold,
- Access to main deck via stern door and shore ramp, and via side doors on Port Side mid ships, and Port Side aft the vessel, using shore ramps,
- Lifted car deck (shelves) on cargo deck,
- Frame spacing of 625 mm.

Main Particulars

Main dimensions:

- Length OA 169.90 m
- Depth to 1st superstructure deck 19.95 m
- Length BP 159.00 m
- Depth to upper deck 14.15 m
- Breadth molded 28,00 m
- Depth to main deck 8,65 m
- Draught designed/scantling 5,90 m /6,20 m
- Light ship weight 10 886 T

Table 1. Draught & Deadweight

Item	Draught	Displacement	Deadweight
Summer (1.025 T/m ³)	6.20 m	18 107 T	6855 T

Calculation of Required Righting Lever

With respect to the criterion 6 of damage stability, the following heeling moments has been calculated for different vessel draughts - 5,00 m, 5,50, and 6,20 m:

Moment Due to the Wind Pressure of 120 N/m²

The results of calculations the above moment due to the wind pressure of 120 N/m², has been presented in Table 2.

Figure 2 The distribution of windage areas for draught of 5.00 meters

Table 2. Moment due to the wind pressure

Draught: 5.00 m					
Item	Area m ²	Wind pr. N/m ²	W. force Tons	VCG m	V.Moment Ton.m
Area 1	1486.80	120.00	8.19	8.08	146.95
Area 2	1533.30	120.00	18.76	18.15	340.42
Area 3	148.80	120.00	1.82	28.20	51.33
Area 4	286.50	120.00	3.50	26.06	91.33
Area 5	50.50	120.00	0.62	26.60	16.43
Area 6	194.50	120.00	2.38	3.10	7.38
Sum Area	3700.00		45.27	14.44	653.00
Displacement at draught 5.00m: 13667.00 T					
Required GZ = 0.088m					
Draught: 5.50 m					
Area 1	1486.80	120.00	18.19	7.83	142.41
Area 2	1533.30	120.00	18.76	17.90	335.73
Area 3	148.80	120.00	1.82	27.95	50.87
Area 4	286.50	120.00	3.50	25.81	90.45
Area 5	50.50	120.00	0.62	26.35	16.28
Area 6	112.60	120.00	1.38	3.10	4.27
Sum Area	3618.50		44.27	14.46	640.01
Displacement at draught 5.50m: 15434.00 T					
Required GZ = 0.081 m					
Draught 6.20 m					
Area 1	1486.80	120.00	18.19	7.48	136.04

Area 2	1533.30	120.00	18.76	17.55	329.17
Area 3	148.80	120.00	1.82	27.60	50.24
Area 4	286.50	120.00	3.50	25.46	89.23
Area 5	50.50	120.00	0.62	26.00	16.06
Sum Area	3505.90		42.89	14.47	620.73
Displacement at draught 6.20m: 18107.00 T					
Required GZ = 0.074 m					

Moment Due to Crowding of All Passengers Towards One Side of the Vessel as per Table 3

Table 3. Moment Due to Crowding of Passengers

Item	Area m ²	No.	Weight kg	Tot.Weight kg	T.Mom Ton.m
Area 1	140.0	4.0	75.0	42000.0	483.0
Area 2	80.0	4.0	75/0	24000.0	240.0
Area 3	30.0	4.0	75.0	9000.0	67.5
Sum Area 250.0 m ²			Sum V.Moment 790.5 Ton.m		
Draught = 5.00 m		Displ. 13667.0 T		Required GZ = 0.098 m	
Draught = 5.50 m		Displ. 15434.0 T		Required GZ = 0.091 m	
Draught = 6.20 m		Displ. 18107.0 T		Required GZ = 0.084 m	

The above calculations were made for the case of launching of survival crafts in one side of the vessel. It should be noted that the vessel is supplied with two Marine Evacuation Systems (RDF Ltd) for both, Port and Starboard side, each consisting of dual track evacuation slide,

embarkation (landing) platform and 14 liferafts (RDF Ltd), for 50 persons each.

Taking into account the greater of the above heeling moments, the results of calculation of the righting arms are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of additional heeling levers

Lever due to the wind pressure:
at draught = 5.0 m 0.088 m
at draught = 5.5 m 0.081 m
at draught = 6.2 m 0.074 m
Lever due to crowding of passengers:
at draught = 5.0 m 0.098 m
at draught = 5.5 m 0.091 m
at draught = 6.2 m 0.084 m
Lever due to launching of survival crafts:
at draught = 5.0 m 0.049m
at draught = 5.5 m 0.048 m
at draught = 6.2 m 0.046 m

Source: M. Szymoński

Stability Calculations

In order to improve the ship safety during the sea voyage, the stability calculations are computerized, getting loading dependent issues, such as results of intact stability, longitudinal strength, and damage stability. Some stability

calculations for the presented vessel are described below.

Loading Conditions for Stability Calculations

The selected loading condition for stability calculations has been shown in Figure 3.

FRESH WATER							
TANK No.	Gamma [t/m ³]	WT [t]	V [m ³]	VCG [m]	LCG [m]	TCG [m]	MFS [tm]
FW30 STORAGE TK. SB	1,000	33,90	33,9	0,93	33,76	1,69	0
FW40 TECHN./BOILER WATER PS	1,000	2,10	2,1	5,61	37,50	-8,15	0
FW44 FOG SPRINKLER SYSTEM	1,000	0,00	0,0	0,00	0,00	0,00	0
TOTAL		36,0		1,20	33,98	1,12	352

HEAVY FUEL OIL							
TANK No.	Gamma [t/m ³]	WT [t]	V [m ³]	VCG [m]	LCG [m]	TCG [m]	MFS [tm]
HFO12 DAY TK. PS	0,960	28,90	30,1	3,57	76,25	-1,48	0
HFO13 SETT. TK. SB	0,960	28,90	30,1	3,57	76,25	1,48	0
TOTAL		57,8		3,57	76,25	-0,00	246

STAB-HEELING							
TANK No.	Gamma [t/m ³]	WT [t]	V [m ³]	VCG [m]	LCG [m]	TCG [m]	MFS [tm]
ST06 STABILIZING TANK	1,000	693,40	693,4	2,55	90,63	0,00	7864
ST07S ANTI HEEL TANK SB	1,000	195,00	195,0	2,28	74,91	12,39	33
ST07P ANTI HEEL TANK PS	1,000	177,00	177,0	2,09	74,90	-12,36	33
ST08 STABILIZING TK.	1,000	875,60	875,6	2,55	75,04	0,00	10009

DIESEL OIL							
TANK No.	Gamma [t/m ³]	WT [t]	V [m ³]	VCG [m]	LCG [m]	TCG [m]	MFS [tm]
MD014 DAY TANK	0,860	21,30	24,6	3,75	64,95	-9,67	0
TOTAL		21,3		3,75	64,95	-9,67	1828

SEWAGE							
TANK No.	Gamma [t/m ³]	WT [t]	V [m ³]	VCG [m]	LCG [m]	TCG [m]	MFS [tm]
MI04 SEWAGE GREY WATER PS	1,000	40,00	40,0	2,56	116,25	-3,33	0
MI05 SEWAGE BLACK WATER SB	1,000	40,00	40,0	2,56	116,25	3,32	0
MI19 SEWAGE VACUUM TK. PS	1,000	10,00	10,0	3,58	67,50	-7,17	0
TOTAL		90,0		2,67	110,83	-0,86	0

WATER BALLAST							
TANK No.	Gamma [t/m ³]	WT [t]	V [m ³]	VCG [m]	LCG [m]	TCG [m]	MFS [tm]
WB01 FOREPEAK	1,016	0,00	0,0	0,00	0,00	0,00	0
WB02 DEEP TANK	1,016	0,00	0,0	0,00	0,00	0,00	0
WB15 DB TANK	1,016	427,63	420,9	0,57	75,00	0,00	0
WB31 DEEP TK.	1,016	0,00	0,0	0,00	0,00	0,00	0
WB32 DEEP TK.	1,016	288,80	284,3	3,83	14,57	0,00	686
TOTAL		716,4		1,88	50,64	0,00	686

CREW, PROVISION etc.						
Description	WT [t]	Frame [t]	Frame [t]	VCG [m]	LCG [m]	TCG [m]
Railwagons Lane 1	0,0	-8	202	10,55	60,30	-10,50
Railwagons Lane 2	0,0	51	230	10,55	85,30	-6,95
Railwagons Lane 3	0,0	-3	241	10,55	74,40	-3,15
Railwagons Lane 4	0,0	39	241	10,55	84,70	3,15
Railwagons Lane 5	0,0	78	230	10,55	93,80	6,95
Railwagons Lane 6	0,0	-8	202	10,55	60,30	10,50
Trailers on main dk	1645,0	0	241	10,60	78,00	0,00
Lorries on upper dk	0,0	-2	243	16,15	80,00	0,00
Trailers on upper dk fwd	1100,0	-2	243	16,15	55,00	0,00
Cars on upper dk fwd	130,0	155	244	15,00	125,00	0,00
Cars on hinged dk	90,0	166	244	17,50	126,00	0,00
Provisionstore	10,0	170	180	24,50	109,40	0,00
Spare parts etc	20,0	81	91	6,50	63,50	0,00
Lub&sludge etc.	25,0	81	91	0,85	63,50	0,00
Crew	5,0	26	242	30,00	94,40	0,00
Drivers	0,0	26	242	23,00	87,50	0,00
Passengers	70,0	26	242	23,00	87,50	0,00
Deck 3	0,0	-8	241	10,55	75,00	-0,17
Deck 4	0,0	-8	243	16,15	85,00	0,00
Deck 5	0,0	166	244	17,50	126,00	0,00
TOTAL	3095,0			13,21	73,18	0,00

TOTAL DEADWEIGHT				
Description	WT [t]	VCG [m]	LCG [m]	TCG [m]
Liquids in Tanks	2862,5	2,35	73,25	0,00
Vehicles	0,0			
Crew, Provision etc.	3095,0	13,21	73,18	0,00
TOTAL	5957,5	7,99	73,22	-0,00

CASE: 07 LOAD-10				
Description	WT [t]	VCG [m]	LCG [m]	TCG [m]
Light Ship	11252,0	12,50	76,64	0,01
Total Deadweight	5957,5	7,99	73,22	0,00
TOTAL	17209,5	10,94	75,45	0,00

Figure 3. Loading conditions of M/F “Polonia”
Source: Loading Manual M/F “Polonia”

The results of stability calculations are presented as the curve of righting arms in function of the heeling angle on Fig.4 and also in Table 5.

Figure 4. The Curve of Righting Arms
Source: M.Szymoński

Table 5. The Righting Arms in Function of Heel

Fi [Deg]	5	10	20	30	40	50	60	70
GZ [m]	0.318	0.637	1.264	1.844	1.926	1.378	0.491	-0.598
The stability complies with criteria of SOLAS'90:								
Stability Criteria	Actual				Required			
GZmax value	GZmax = 1.97 m				0.20 m			
GZmax angle	Fi = 36.25°				30.0°			
Metacentric height corr	GMc = 3.51 m				2.98 m			
Area under GZ up to 30°	A30° = 0.493 mrad				0.055mrad			
Area under GZ up to 40°	A40° = 0.835 mrad				0.090mrad			
Area between 30°-40°	A30°-40°=0.342mrad				0.030mrad			
Angle of heel due to crowding of passengers	Ap = 0.93°				10.00°			
Angle of heel due to turning	At = 3.17°				10.00°			
IMO Weather Criterion	K = 2.198				1.00			
Heeling lever of lateral wind force	Lw1 = 0.148 m							
Angle of roll to windward due to wind action	F1 = 24.74°							
Angle of downflooding	FiD = 44.6°							
List	Fi = 0.1°							

Source: M.Szymoński

Damage Stability Calculations

For the loading conditions described in section 4, two damage situations have been simulated. First of them concerns the flooding of dry spaces and water ballast tank in fore part of the double bottom and section below the main deck of the vessel: dry space (SP01) in double bottom, deep tank (WB02) and dry space (SP03).

The double bottom compartments layout is shown in Figure 5. The water ballast tanks are marked green colour, dry spaces are white, fuel and oil tanks are red and grey, and fresh water tanks are blue.

The results of calculations the hypothetical cases of damage some of double bottom compartments are presented in this paper.

The results have been obtained by use of the vessel's stability calculation software.

Case of Damage in Fore Part of the Vessel

In this case only 3 compartments in fore part of the vessel has been damaged, as per Fig. 6. The vessel in this state has a good stability and will float in equilibrium position. The damage stability complies with criteria of SOLAS'90 and Stockholm Agreement.

Figure 5. The Ship Compartments Layout
Source: Loading Manual M/F “Polonia”.

Figure 6. Horizontal Section of Flooded Fore Part Compartments
Source: M.Szymoński

The results of stability calculations for the above damage case, are presented in Figure 7. In this case the main parameters of ship's stability are:

Metacentric height corrected $GMc = 2.9$ m.
 Righting arm $GZ \max = 0.54$ m with no water on the train deck.

With water on the Ro-Ro deck the righting arm $GZ \max = 0.53$ m.

The water level on Ro-Ro deck is 0.03 m.
 The Freeboard = 1.19 m.

When the water occurs on the Ro-Ro deck, the stability results correspond not only with criteria of SOLAS '90 but with Stockholm Agreement, too.

Figure 7. The Results of Damage Stability Calculations for the Above Case
 Source: M.Szymoński

Case of damage in the middle sections of the vessel

This case corresponds the flooding of following dry spaces in the midship's part of the double bottom of the vessel: SP 13, SP 14, SP 15 and SP 11-12.

The vessel's damage, presented in this point corresponds the situation of the stability loss when the 0.13 m of water accumulated on Ro – Ro deck. The damaged volumes of the vessel are located in the double bottom and below of the main deck of the midships, as it has been shown in Figure 8.

With no water on the Ro – Ro deck the vessel has a small stability margin, but she will float in equilibrium position. The stability is however

not sufficient to comply with criteria of SOLAS'90, as presented in Figure 9.

Figure 8. Horizontal Section of Flooded Compartments
 Source: M.Szymoński

Figure 9. The Results of Stability Calculations for the Case of Flooding the Midship's Compartments as per Figure 8
 Source: M.Szymoński

Conclusion

Results of stability and damage stability calculations, presented in this paper are getting knowledge of practice in simplified stability information for the master. It's a very important element of safety management on the Ro-Ro Vessel.

Author of the paper, having the practice as the master of M/F "Polonia", is also experienced that absolute safety doesn't exist, and a large number of safety measures are difficult to execute.

The results of the above calculations are giving proof of the significance of simplified stability information for the master and tools for fast verification: if a vessel sinks or staying afloat.

The analyse of case, regarding to the damage of the fore spaces of the vessel, is testifying that the vessel is staying afloat, even if 40 tons of sea water is flooding the main deck.

The next case corresponds to the sinking of the vessel due to the damage of four spaces in the

midship's. The 195 tons of the sea water is coming to flood the main, open un-subdivided deck and results in the stability loss.

The stability calculations presented in this paper were performed by using the certified vessel's software for loading and stability calculations according to SOLAS 2009 and Stockholm Agreement (1997).

References

Loading Manual of Ro-Ro / passenger ship, unpublished.

Resolution MSC.267 (85). (2008). Adoption of the International Code on Intact Stability. Retrieved from [https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/KnowledgeCentre/IndexofIMOResolutions/MSCResolutions/MSC.267\(85\).pdf](https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/KnowledgeCentre/IndexofIMOResolutions/MSCResolutions/MSC.267(85).pdf)

Szymoński, M. (2013). Analysis and Evaluation of Manoeuvrability Characteristics of Polish Ferries M/F "Polonia" and M/F "Gryf". *2The Journal on Marine Navigation and Safety of Sea*

Transportation, 7(4), 515-518.
<http://doi.org/10.12716/1001.07.04.06>

Szymoński, M. (2019). *Some Notes on Risk and Safety Evaluation of Ro-Ro Passenger Ships Exploitation*. Proceedings from IEEE, 2019 European Navigation Conference (ENC). Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, New Jersey
<https://doi.org/10.1109/EURONAV.2019.8714157>

Szymoński, M. (2021). Stockholm Agreement Analysis for Ro-Ro Passenger Ships Navigating in the North European Waters and the Baltic Sea, 2021, *Transnav, The Journal on Marine Navigation and Safety of Sea Transportation*, 15(2), 423-429.

<https://doi.org/10.12716/1001.15.02.22>

Technical documentation of M/F “Polonia”, unpublished.